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TRANSMISSION AND EPIDEMIC OF DENGUE
AND ITS ABATEMENT IN ISLAMABAD CAPITAL TERRITORY, PAKISTAN

*Muhammad Najeeb Durrani¹, Muhammad Aslam Khan², Muhammad Babar Alam³, Muhammad Shoaib Akhtar² and Asif Hanif⁴

Communicable Disease Surveillance Cell, Health Department, Islamabad

²University of Health Sciences Lahore-54600, Pakistan

³Dengue Cell, Department of Zoology, LCW University, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴WHO Sub Office Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

⁵Postgraduate Medical Institute, Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan

*Corresponding author: dr.durrani@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Dengue fever has become endemic in most parts of the country since past several years. The incidence of this simmering epidemic has not been felt to the same extent in preceding years, as has been in 2011, with cases and deaths. The district health authorities in Islamabad were well aware of the grave situation arising out of the major outbreak in Lahore, under took measures trying to prepare for the prevention and control of Dengue Fever in Islamabad, since the beginning of the epidemic. Immediate stringent measures were taken under the supervision of Capital Administrative and Administrative Division (CA&DD) from the platform of a National Task force with the collaborative support of many stake holders to pre-empt the situation mainly to prevent, control the Dengue Fever spread in Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT). Keeping in view the previous year's data and the fact that the expected rapid human travel during the festival of Eid-ul-Fiter occurring in first week of September 2011, and suspected transport of infected vector through goods may make the spilling of the infection in neighboring districts, effective and timely pre-emptive measures were taken. As expected like many parts of the country the federal capital experienced the epidemic of Dengue Fever with 1000 suspected cases of which 624 confirmed and there were 2 deaths as per data recorded on culmination of the 49th epidemiological week. The case fatality rate, however, remained very low: 0.3%. The situation in Islamabad remained moderate as per evidence that the epidemic was largely confined to Dengue Fever and not the Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever or Dengue Shock Syndrome.

Key Words: Dengue virus, Epidemic, Islamabad, Pakistan, Mosquitoes

1. INTRODUCTION

Dengue, the most widespread mosquito-borne infection in human beings, is now endemic and an emerging problem in Pakistan. It started from the southern coastal parts of Baluchistan in 1994. After a long silence the disease struck again in 2003 in North Western Parts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) Province and some parts of the Punjab. It has now become a regular feature appearing yearly in summer and reaching its peak in autumn in most parts of the country including Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK). Dengue Fever (DF) / Dengue Haemorrhagic Fever (DHF) are acute viral disease having the potential of causing large scale outbreaks. The risk of dengue has shown an increase in recent years due to rapid urbanization, life style changes and deficient water management including improper water storage practices in urban, peri-urban and rural areas, leading to proliferation of mosquito breeding sites.

Aedes aegypti and *Aedes albopictus*, the vector mosquito of Dengue, breed in tree-holes, man-made containers, viz., cement tanks, overhead water tanks, tires, room coolers, pitchers, discarded containers,

etc. The disease tends to follow seasonal pattern, i.e., the cases peaking after monsoon rain (July–August) but not uniformly distributed.

There was already enormous burden of preventable and communicable diseases in the country that the emergence of DF and DHF are becoming increasingly important and have emerged as major public health problem in Pakistan, causing major outbreaks in recent years.

First known dengue outbreak occurred in Karachi, Sindh Province, in 1994 (from June 1994–September 1995). A total of 145 patients were admitted in the hospitals with one death. That outbreak was confirmed due to multiple serotypes of dengue virus (DENV).

Then in October 1995 there was another outbreak of febrile illness in southern Baluchistan Province, bordering Karachi, which occurred in the workers of a construction company of power generation plant. Laboratory investigations confirmed 57 out of 76 persons as positive for DF.

After 8 years of silence, in September 2003, the

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disease appeared in North Western Part of the country in District Haripur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) Province. It claimed 6 lives and caused morbidity among 700 persons. The 2003 outbreak in Haripur was due to DENV-type 2. Meanwhile another outbreak reported from SoanSakeser Valley, District Khushab, in the Punjab Province. National Institute of Virology, South Africa, confirmed that 7 out of 11 samples sent were positive for HAI and IgM antibody due to DENV type-2. (Figure. 1&Figure2).

Later in November 2005, dengue appeared in Karachi. Cases were more of undifferentiated fever and also hemorrhagic fever. It followed by a second more severe wave of Dengue outbreak in 2006. It subsided in severity but some cases continued appearing and in late October 2006, it assumed the form of a big epidemic. Again, in April 2007, it reappeared and persisted till December 2007. Historical summary of dengue outbreak in Pakistan from 1995 to 2011 is given in Table 1. In the later years the scientific evidence of data showed a decline as shown in Fig. 3. However, an ever-increasing rise in the cases and deaths in many remote rural areas attributed to the gradual spread of DENV.

The study, first of its kind in Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT), was done with the aim to identify various factors affecting the population at risk and the high-risk areas due to the disease and to develop interventions for the future outbreaks.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It is a hospital based study conducted to determine various factors and evaluates the 2011 dengue outbreak in ICT wherein 999 admitted patient data were recorded and their different disease profile were analyzed. A surveillance cell was established from the beginning of the outbreaks in the office of the Health Department ICT for monitoring the trend and other activities required for the study. Inclusion criterion was all those patients who reported with dengue fever symptoms and admitted to indoor health facility by the clinician or on the basis of laboratory tests. There was no age limit, nor any restriction to the area from where the patients were coming from. A line list was provided to the hospitals to collect basic epidemiological information about the admitted patients comprising of name, age, sex, address, date of onset of symptoms, date of admission, type of test performed and its result and outcome of the patient. Exclusion criteria were OPD patients and those who were reported from other primary health facilities or from the private sector hospitals or mere information

from the laboratory.

1.1 Current outbreak in Islamabad Capital Territory:

In view of the national scenario emerging from the unexpected rapid spread of Dengue Fever in most parts of the country in 2011, and to safeguard the federal capital, the CA&DD under its mandate to provide medical cover to the inhabitants of the ICT constituted a Task Force comprising of Executive Directors of the three territory care hospitals, Directorate of Health CDA, ICT Health Department, Federal Directorate of Education under the Chairmanship of the undersigned. The Task force held daily meeting and took regular stocks of the following critical areas:

- Hospitals' related activities for providing timely and effective clinical care to the patients;
- Hospital based surveillance and monitoring of the disease in major hospitals of ICT to identify high risk areas and the population most affected to plan timely interventions;
- Public Awareness campaigns through Lady Health Workers (LHW) and also by inclusion of the education Sector;
- Ensuring availability of insecticides, mosquito repellants for domestic use, in the market;
- Fumigation and residual spraying at high risk areas and where confirmed patients were being reported.

2.2 Prevention and Control Efforts

The Islamabad Administration with the help of different stake holders of public health authorities and private organization had taken immediate stringent pre-emptive measures to prevent, control and contain the Dengue Fever in ICT. The ICT Administration keeping in view the gravity of the major outbreak in Lahore. In first phase after a meeting under the Chairmanship of D.C/Director Health, ICT, on 23rd August, 2011, first round of Fumigation and Spray was initiated in three sectors, i.e., Bharakau, Tarlai and Sihala. Consequently 3 teams were constituted that carried out the campaign in the rural areas which was completed on 30th August 2011. Another meeting of all stakeholders held on 07th of September 2011, was chaired by the Chief Commissioner, ICT. It was attended by the DC/Director Health, DHO Islamabad, Senior Medical Officers of the Health Department, representatives from NIH and major Hospitals of Islamabad, besides WHO Surveillance Officer Islamabad, to develop a joint strategy to mitigate the spread of disease in the capital by strengthening

surveillance activities and ensuring stockpiling of the medicines and availability of beds in the hospitals.

Accordingly an intensive campaign for vector control and creating awareness in general public for preventing them from the bite of mosquitoes was launched. The 2nd phase of campaign was initiated and almost all the major villages of ICT were fumigated and spray out for vector control. The following activities were carried out including:

A) Establishment of Dengue Fever Prevention and Control Cell on 15th September 2011, to coordinate all the activities and to collect and disseminate the information.

- Surveillance and monitoring was out for early detection of new cases and identifying geographical background of the admitted ones in different Hospitals of ICT.
- Situational Analysis: Detailed data from admitted patients from all the five major hospitals of Islamabad was regularly collected and updated, a daily comprehensive report developed for the stakeholders to take prompt and timely action/response. The data was shared with stakeholders for offering a rapid response to admitted cases belonging to ICT Urban area. While ICT rural area cases were timely responded by the Health Department ICT through its rapid response team for providing fogging and residual spray in the affected areas for vector control. (Table 1, Figures 4, 5 & 6)
- Launching of Web Site (ictadministration.gov.pk) for displaying actions carried out by Islamabad Administration regarding prevention and control of dengue fever. The data generated in the health Department ICT regularly displayed at the site.

B) Vector Control.

- In three rounds 832 mozas, dhokes, mohallahs and various premises of 133 villages spread over in 12 Union Councils of ICT, were fumigated and sprayed.
- 39 schools and 35 public places, Government offices including NIH, Health Services Academy, Froby schools, Police Station, Police Training College Sihala, etc., were fumigated and sprayed.
- 19 Water supply Tanks/Reservoir chlorinated by the Local Government.
- 37 filling of ponds/treatment with kerosene oil.

C) Awareness campaign by the Health Department and UC/Revenue staff.

Total number of 120,000 pamphlets bearing health education message for prevention and control of DF were distributed. Out of which

22,000 pamphlets distributed to approximately 21,320 houses through 333 LHWs in rural ICT and 35,000 handed over to Federal Directorate of Education for distribution in various school located in ICT. Besides Health Facilities, District Population Welfare Office, Islamabad Police, Traffic Police, public places including bank, restaurant, chemist shop are also been provided with pamphlets for distribution,

- 15 banners containing public messages displayed at various public places in rural areas.
- One hour radio Talk-Show conducted in Traffic Police FM Channel on 10th September 2011, for awareness of general public. Health Education and information session conducted in Traffic Police Office, Sector F-8/1, and Committee Room of DPWO at G-9 Markaz, Islamabad. In addition, health education and information sessions were also held at Barakau, Tarlai, Sihala and Ali Pur where a large number of people from various walks of life participated in the session.
- Lady Health Supervisors were trained to supervise and conduct training of LHWs working in rural ICT and urban slums to visit every house in their respective areas to motivate the community about adopting the preventive measures for the prevention and control of DF. In this regard LHWs conducted the visit of 35789 houses in rural Islamabad, Katchiabadies and urban slums.
- 500 Mortein repellent lotion were distributed to the residents of France Colony and Urban slums in Sector F-7, Islamabad.

Key actions undertaken were stringent and sustained public health response jointly with civic bodies, awareness campaign for community and enhanced diagnostic facilities with efficient medical services. A Dengue cell was established at the federal level in the Health Department ICT that was monitoring the outbreak with the assistance of provincial health departments.

Since the community participation is of essence to the entire effort, to contain and prevent the disease and avoid recurrence of DF and DHF, a sustained level of social mobilization was done. Accordingly, communities were mobilized to undertake effective vector control measures, especially in the areas from where the cases were reported.

In this regard, mass awareness campaigns and interpersonal communication activities were carried out to make the community realize the importance of eliminating mosquito breeding sites inside their homes, and adopting safe water storage practices,

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besides personal protection through protective clothing as well as use of indoor sprays. Resultantly the incidence of DF and DHF in 2007, was comparatively less in terms of morbidity and mortality as was seen in 2006. However, if the efforts are not sustained the scientific evidence suggests severer epidemics in future. The public health measures taken by the Government further need to be complimented at individual, community levels and by other sectors for the prevention and control of DF in Pakistan.

3.3 Public sector and stakeholder's role

The Government realized the importance and accordingly provided necessary directions and the required support at all levels, which includes insecticides, larvicides as well as financial assistance for capacity building through trainings. The WHO and UNICEF also provided additional, technical support in the form of Guidelines, Advisories, laboratory items, capacity building of school teachers and epidemiological investigations.

3. RESULTS

A hospital based cross-sectional investigation was carried out in Islamabad Capital Territory's five major hospitals, including four public and one private, catering major bulk of the patients suffering from suspected Dengue Fever disease (Table 2). A line-list was developed for the DF suspected patients being admitted in Islamabad hospitals and data was received on regular basis to monitor the monthly trend, (Figure 7, 8) and to identify high risk areas for managing current and future outbreaks and take timely response from where the positive patients were being reported (Figures 5, 6 & 7).

As expected, that the Islamabad being well developed for medical services might attract a large bulk of patients from other areas, it was found that most of the patients belonged to areas other ICT, e.g., KPK, Punjab and AJK. As many as 49% of patients admitted in ICT hospitals were from other areas while 40% were from the ICT urban areas and 11% from the ICT rural community (Figure 6). Monthly trend of dengue fever cases showed peak in October and then there is a sharp fall (Figure 8). It is ascribed to the post October gradual fall in temperature.

There is a very little difference between the suspected and confirmed patients and as the samples were not taken in the recommended time frame. Most of the patients who were tested negative were actually false negative hence the probability of confirmed patients to be more (Figure 5).

Monitoring of the epidemic revealed a typical epidemic curve from 31st week to 49th week (Figures 7 & 9) enabling us to plan future timely interventions.

Males and people of Age-Group of 20-30 years' are at higher risk of getting dengue viral infection as compared to the other age groups, as shown in the Figures 10 & 11, those who were from the working class had the highest tendency to catch infection. Mean age group from the data analysis showed that population strata of 20-35 years while the number of infected children were very little (Table 3).

77% of the patients were males while only 23% were females showing the possibility that most of the women who remain properly clad usually remaining indoors and more exposed males were bitten outside. However, we cannot rule out bites inside houses as in most of the cases family members were all bitten one after the other showing the presence of infected vector inside homes.

The only two deaths that occurred were from outside Islamabad. Both were male age 63 and 65 years in September and November 2011.

Data revealed different high risk areas in urban and rural settings (Figures 13 & 14) demanding to take timely prevention and control measures in these places identified in the current spell of dengue fever in Islamabad.

4. DISCUSSION

Aedes aegypti and *Aedes albopictus* are well known vectors of dengue virus. However, there is no clear documented evidence available as to which *Aedes* species is spreading the disease in Islamabad. The opinion of experts is divided on the subject. Most of the entomologists opine about *Aedes aegypti* but still some see both the species as culprit, as both are anthropophilic and active during day. They breed in artificial containers and tree holes. Unfortunately no study is available about the population dynamic and density of *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* as well as about other mosquito species of *Aedes*, *Anopheles* and *Culex* in Islamabad. Aslamkhan and Salman (1967) have shown the preference of *Aedes albopictus* to breed in tree holes *vis a vis* artificial containers, which is the preference of *Aedes aegypti*. Islamabad is not comparable with other cities of Pakistan. It is open and clean with lots of parks and trees all over, with expected tree holes and very few artificial containers, and debris as breeding places. Our study also suggests the possibility of *Aedes albopictus* as the main vector since firstly, most of the affected persons ranged from the 20 to 30 years of age and secondly, majority of the patients were males leading to the hypothesis that the bites occurred outside the residence. Thus on its basis we can

conclude that: The major biting mosquito is not the *Aedes aegypti* alone but it is the *Aedes albopictus*, which is causing the current transmission ICT.

Constraints/ grey areas and future requirements

The influence of the disease in short term has faded but there is no question that it will not reoccur next summer as the dried up tree holes and artificial containers may be harboring dried up eggs of both the species waiting to be submerged in water of the next rainy season.

There are many lessons to be learnt from this traumatizing encounter. There is a clear and palpable need to take tangible steps to ensure that in future the risk of the disease is minimized.

Both epidemiological and entomological research is required to determine exactly the species of dengue vector, i.e., *Aedes aegypti* or *Aedes albopictus* and other *Stegomyia* mosquito species prevalence in Islamabad. The current constraints and lacunae as assessed in monitoring the outbreak are given in following points:

- Study the Biological behavior of the mosquito and the burden of disease it has caused need to be studied. Research is required in determining the species of mosquito in endemic areas, its approximate number and habitat.
- The application of vector control methods, including source reduction, use of chemical larvicide and adulticides and of biological control agents was not done due to lack of resources and availability of entomologically qualified personnel.
- WHO approved insecticides were to be procured and their quality needs to be tested to avoid waste of resources and precious human force.
- Plan the programme capacity; devise well-defined indicators and programme targets, and better understanding of efficacy and cost-effectiveness of control measures particularly in terms of reducing transmission.
- Laboratory tests according to the recommended kits on ELIZA was not conducted in some of the hospitals as the investigation revealed that only Poly Clinics and KRL Hospital were doing tests on ELIZA through NIH while the PIMS and CDA hospital were performing tests on rapid kits. Shifa International Hospital in private sector was doing the tests on ELIZA.
- Serotyping of DEVV was not done either by the private sector or the public sector though KRL Hospital planned to do it.
- Capital Development Authority Sanitation wing has to join their efforts with other relevant sections for ensuring the safe and quick disposal of solid waste, in order to prevent mosquitoes from

laying their eggs in potential water-holding rubbish. Community also needs to be educated about the importance of quick solid waste disposal as it may contain potential breeding containers for *Aedes* mosquitoes.

- Understanding of the virus transmission dynamics and the identification of transmission thresholds was seen as one of the major epidemiological and operational research challenges. A coordinated response was required by all the sectors.

- Besides all above mentioned points the operational research is needed based on lessons learnt in the current epidemic as it was observed that there are critical gaps in the cycle from data generation to its eventual appropriate use in developing strategies and better targeted interventions to avoid unnecessary wastage of resources.

Recommendations/ Suggested actions for Dengue prevention and control

In post October scenario the brunt of the epidemic has been diffused due to cold weather reduced the vector mosquitoes population.

The existing measures under taken by the Health Department, for the control of Dengue Fever during August to October 2011 in Islamabad, certainly need to be complemented.

Following are the points recommended on the basis of this investigation study to effectively prevent and control future outbreaks:

- Fever Surveillance through sentinel sites in public/private hospitals.
- Strengthening of referral system
- Epidemic preparedness and response
- Entomological Surveillance
- Larval surveys
- Vector Control
- Anti-larval measures
- Source reduction
- Personal protection
- Fogging during outbreaks
- Enactment and enforcement of legislations (Building and Civic Byelaws) to contain anti-mosquito conditions
- Behavior Change Communication for scaling up community participation
- Inter-sectoral convergence
- Human Resource Development through capacity building
- Operational research
- Monitoring and supervision
- Role of Sterile Insect Technique (SIT) and other biological and genetic control strategies.

Figure1: Number of Dengue Fever cases Reported in various area of Pakistan rom 1994 – 2005.

Figure 2: Number of Dengue Fever cases Reported and Confirmed in various area of Pakistan rom 2996 - 2011

Figure 3: Number of Suspected Dengue Fever cases Reported from various area of Pakistan in 2005, 2006 and 2007.

Figure 4: Number of Deaths from Suspected and confirmed Dengue Fever cases reported from Islamabad from 2006 to 2011

Figure 5: Number of Suspected and confirmed cases of Dengue Fever admitted in various Hospital in Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 6: Number of Suspected cases of Dengue Fever from ICT Urban, ICT Rural and other areas admitted in various Hospital in Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 7: Weekly admittance of dengue suspected Patients in IVT Hospital as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 8: Monthly Trend of Suspected cases of Dengue Fever admitted in various Hospital in Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 9: Epidemiological weekly Trend of Suspected cases of Dengue Fever Outbreak admitted in various Hospital in Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 10: Gender Distribution of Suspected and confirmed cases of Dengue Fever admitted in various Hospital in Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 11: Age Distribution of Suspected and confirmed cases of Dengue Fever admitted in various Hospital in Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 12: Number of Suspected and confirmed cases of Dengue Fever from other Provinces admitted in various Hospital in Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 13: Number of Suspected and Confirmed cases of Dengue Fever admitted in Hospital from various Rural Areas of in Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

Figure 14: Number of Suspected and Confirmed cases of Dengue Fever admitted in Hospital from various Urban Sectors of Islamabad as of December 8, 2011.

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Table 1. Historical summary of Dengue Virus outbreaks in Pakistan 1994 – 2011.

Area	Period	Number of cases	Lab confirmed	Mortality
Karach, Sindh	1994 Jun - Sep 1995	145	5	1
Baluchistan	1995 Oct	76	57	0
Haripur, KPK	2003 Sep	700	6	9
Khushab, Punjab	2003 Oct	2000	7	3
Karachi, Sindh	2005 Sep - Dec	270	43	7
Karachi, Sindh	2011 Aug - Dec	<5000	881	5

Table 2. shows a report generated on the daily basis of dengue cases in various hospitals of ICT

Sr. No.	Name of mHospital	Suspected Admissions/Referrals			Still Admitted	Discharged	Positive			Deaths		
		Previous	Last 24 Hrs	Cumulative			Previous	Last 24 Hrs	Cumulative	Previous	Last 24 Hrs	Cumulative
1	PAKISTAN INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES (PIMS)	481	0	482	2	480	380	0	380	0	0	0
2	FG POLY CLINIC HOSPITAL	262	0	262	0	262	94	0	94	0	0	0
3	CAPITAL HOSPITAL	68	0	68	0	68	46	0	46	0	0	0
4	SHIFA INTERNATIONAL	146	0	146	0	146	83	0	83	2	0	2
5	KRL HOSPITAL	42	0	42	0	42	21	0	21	0	0	0
	TOTAL :-	999	0	1000	2	998	624	0	624	2	0	2

Table 3. Age Distribution of Patients admitted in Islamabad Hospitals

Age group in years	Number of infected person
0 - 5	6
6 - 14	52
15 - 24	300
25 - 34	271
35 - 44	160
45 - 54	109
55 - 64	45
65 +	57

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